

This is a master time mirror time master clock, in other words a fusion reactor:



Notes:

This clock contains:

- The 12 counter-clockwise roots.
- The 24 clockwise roots.
- The momentum hand.
- The second hand.
- The split minute hand.
- The hourly hand.
- The gap hand.
- The cycle hand.
- The mirror hand.
- The breakthrough hand, a sunned compass.

Red earth iron that is steamed for the encasement.

Flamed grey steel for the oven.

The side view of the reactor:



Offset sphere 1.



